

**Survey within the framework
of the project "LATILL - Level-Adequate Texts in Language Learning"**

Dear GFL/GSL colleagues:

We would like to ask you about your experiences with reading texts. We invite you to answer the questions in the questionnaire, which aims to collect information about the selection and use of reading texts in German as a Foreign and Second Language (GFL/GSL) classes.

The results of the survey will be used for the EU project "LATILL - Level- Adequate Texts in Language Learning" (www.germ.univie.ac.at/projekt/latill, <https://grial.usal.es/latill>), which aims to improve strategies and selection criteria for reading texts, to support the teaching of reading skills for different language levels and to adapt it to pedagogical needs.

The questionnaire takes about 15 minutes to complete. Participation in this survey is voluntary; there are no disadvantages to non-participation or dropping out. The data will be collected and analysed anonymously and used exclusively for scientific publications on the above objective. Thank you for your cooperation.

Question Group A: Personal data

1. In which country do you currently teach GFL/GSL?

[Field for free text input]

2. In which educational sector do you teach GFL/GSL?

- primary school
- secondary school
- university
- adult education

[Filter question for questions 7-11]

3. What kind of GFL/GSL courses do you teach?

- language course
- reading course
- technical language, e.g. GFL/GSL for technical professions
- translation and interpretation
- others, namely:

4. At which levels do you teach GFL/GSL?

- A1

- A2
- B1
- B2
- C1
- C2
- no CEFR levels

5. How many years of teaching experience do you have?

[Field for entering numerical values]

Group of questions B: Learning objectives and text types

6. To promote which competences and skills do you choose reading texts for GFL/GSL classes? (You can select several options)

- reading skills (learning to read)
- phonetic competence
- lexical competence
- grammatical competence
- media competence
- oral expression
- written expression
- listening comprehension
- reading comprehension
- others, namely:

[Questions 7-11:

Depending on the information provided in question 2, different questions are displayed. If "secondary school" is selected, questions 8 and 9 are displayed].

7. Which types of texts do you choose for learners in primary school?

- narrative
- message
- report
- reportage
- technical
- interview
- SMS, message from a messaging service (e.g. WhatsApp)
- blog entry
- advertisement, advertising text
- letter, e-mail

- poem
- song
- drama
- an extract from an artwork
- table, diagram, etc.
- utility texts, e.g. instructions for use, leaflet, contract, etc.
- dialogue
- others, namely:

8. Which types of texts do you choose for learners in lower secondary education?

[Answer options as in question 7]

9. Which types of texts do you choose for learners in upper secondary education?

[Answer options as in question 7]

10. Which types of texts do you choose for learners at university?

[Answer options as in question 7]

11. Which types of texts do you choose for learners in adult education?

[Answer options as in question 7]

Question Group C: Selection of texts

12. How important are the following aspects for you when using reading texts in GFL/GSL classes?

- level of difficulty of the texts
- relation to the themes of the curriculum
- correspond to the language levels of the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (A1 - C2).
- authenticity
- topicality
- adequacy of content
- availability of didactic material on the text
- motivating theme for pupils

[Grid with response options: very important - important - less important - not important]

13. Which aspects of culture should the reading texts for GFL/GSL classes contain information on?

- history
- geography
- politics
- religion
- traditions
- literature
- music
- art
- leisure
- sports
- none at all
- others, namely:

14. Which textbook do you use?

[Field for free text input]

15. How would you rate your GFL/GSL textbook regarding the appropriateness and functionality of the reading texts?

- very good
- good
- average
- not very satisfactory
- unsatisfactory

16. How would you rate your GFL/GSL textbook in terms of the motivational value of the reading texts?

- very good
- good
- average
- not very satisfactory
- unsatisfactory

17. What could be improved in terms of text selection in your GFL/GSL textbook?

[Field for free text input]

18. How often do you look for reading texts on your own for GFL/GSL lessons?

- generally
- frequently

- sometimes
- rarely
- never

[Filter question for questions 19-27]

[Questions 19-27 do not appear if "never" has been indicated in question 18.]

19. Which criteria do you use to select texts?

- keywords/topics
- number of known and unknown words
- length of the text
- grammatical complexity of the text
- presence of graphic supports (story cards, comparative tables)
- images
- others, namely:

20. Where do you look for reading texts for GFL/GSL classes?

- on the Internet
- in a national GFL textbook
- in a GFL/GSL textbook by a German publisher
- in a reading book
- others, namely:

[Filter question for question 21]

[Question 21 only appears if "in a national GFL textbook"/"in a GFL/GSL textbook by a German publisher" has been indicated in question 21.]

21. In which GFL/GSL textbook do you look for the texts?

[Field for free text input]

22. Do you know of any particular system/programme or website to search for reading texts for GFL/GSL classes?

- yes
- no

[Filter question for question 23(-27)].

[Question 23(-27) only appears if "yes" has been indicated in question 22.]

23. Do you use particular search systems/programmes or websites to search for reading texts for GFL/GSL classes?

- yes
- partially
- no

[Filter question for questions 25-28]

[Questions 24-27 do not appear if "no" has been indicated in question 23.]

24. Which of the following systems/programmes or websites for finding reading texts for GFL/GSL classes have you ever used?

- Deutsche Welle
- KANSAS
- deutschalsfremdsprache.ch
- derdiedaf.com
- lingua.com
- vitaminade/s
- deutsch-perfekt/com
- others, namely:

25. What determines your choice of these sources and programmes for selecting reading texts?

- availability of texts
- authority of the supplier
- relevance of the offer
- ease of access
- functional design
- others, namely:

26. How do you rate search platforms in terms of search options and selecting reading texts?

- very good
- good
- average
- not very satisfactory
- unsatisfactory

27. What other search and selection options would you like to see?

[Field for free text input]

Question Group D: Working with texts

28. Which task formats do you associate with the use of reading texts?

- closed tasks to ensure comprehension (e.g. true/false, cloze texts, picture headline assignments)
- semi-open-ended comprehension tasks (e.g., answering questions, summarising)
- tasks with a gaming component (e.g. a quiz)
- open-ended tasks after the reading (e.g. discussion, writing a text on the topic)
- read aloud
- searching for specific vocabulary or structures in the text
- none at all
- others, namely:

29. Which reading strategies do you use with learners before reading?

- form hypotheses about the type of text, its content, etc.
- focus on headings, graphic highlighting and pictures
- ask questions about the text
- work on semantic fields
- none at all
- others, namely:

30. Which reading strategies do you use with learners during reading?

- interrupt the reading and formulate hypotheses or questions
- silent reading
- writing a reading-learner diary
- mark known words in the text
- cross out unknown words that are not necessary for the understanding of the text
- identify words through internationalisms, the mother tongue, another foreign language, the rules of derivation inherent in the language, the context
- underlining, structuring, noting keywords
- work with the dictionary
- summarise sections
- others, namely:

31. Which reading strategies do you use with students after reading?

- point out the main ideas/theme of the different sections of the text
- summarise the text in one sentence
- describe your emotional reactions to what you have read (e.g. with literary texts)
- report on the content of the whole text
- find subtitles
- represent a part of the text (for literary texts)

- create images/graphic representations of the text
- write alternatives to the text (find another end, ...)
- write a commentary/critique on the text
- search for more information about the text on the Internet
- plan and carry out a debate for and against
- plan and carry out a survey on the topic
- others, namely:

32. Do you work with learners with special needs (visually impaired)?

- yes
- no

[Filter question for question 33.]

[Question 33 only appears if "yes" has been indicated in question 32.]

33. What is especially important for you in reading texts for learners with special needs (visually impaired) in GFL/GSL classes?

- adjustment of the font size
- colour accents in important linguistic aspects
- contrast and brightness settings
- built-in audio accompaniment / read-aloud function
- note-taking
- maximum number of words and long sentences
- others, namely:

34. Here you have the opportunity to leave your opinion or comments on this survey:

[Field for free text entry].